

A Novel Fusion Ranking Multi-Query Method for Image Retrieval and its Application in Skin Disease Diagnosis

Huy Tran Van,^{1,*} Tuyet Dao Van,^{2,†} Khoi Ngo Nguyen,^{3,‡} Sergey Ablameyko,^{4,§} Huy Ngo Hoang,^{5,¶} and Doan Nguyen Van^{6,**}

¹*Hong Duc University, Thanh Hoa, VIETNAM*

²*University of Cuu Long, Vinh Long Province, VIETNAM*

³*Pitech lab, Innotech AI Solutions, Ha Noi, VIETNAM*

⁴*Belarusian State University, 4 Nezavisimosti av., Minsk, 220030, BELARUS^{††}*

⁵*CMC University, Ha Noi, VIETNAM*

⁶*Electric Power University, Ha Noi, VIETNAM*

(Received 5 August, 2025)

The detection of skin diseases is crucial due to their visibility and potential for transmission. However, clinical diagnosis presents challenges, often proving time-consuming and ineffective. Consequently, there is a pressing need for content-based image retrieval (CBIR) techniques to automate the detection of skin diseases. Effective multi-faceted ranking algorithms are widely used in CBIR, representing images through low-level features (color, texture, shape) and high-level features extracted from Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Low-level features enable rapid detection of visual differences and are invariant to rotation and translation. Conversely, CNN-derived high-level features provide a richer semantic description. However, single query image systems may not fully capture image complexity, leading to inaccurate retrieval. This study introduces a novel method to improve the accuracy of skin disease image retrieval by combining ranking results from multiple query images. By integrating information from two input images, the proposed method enhances retrieval accuracy and efficiency. This approach leverages diverse semantic information for a more comprehensive and accurate retrieval process. Experiments on the Dermnet dataset demonstrate the effectiveness of this method in improving image retrieval quality.

AMS Subject Classification: 68W99

Keywords: Multiquery, Combine Ranking, Content-based image retrieval (CBIR), Efficient Manifold Ranking (EMR).

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17950296>

1. Introduction

The rapid advancements in image processing and computer vision have led to their widespread integration into various fields, including

healthcare. Medical image processing plays a crucial role in disease detection, particularly in dermatology [1, 2]. Skin diseases are often diagnosed based on visual features such as color, shape, and texture. However, the subtle differences between healthy and diseased skin regions can make diagnosis challenging, often requiring the expertise of experienced dermatologists.

Content-Based Image Retrieval (CBIR) has emerged as a promising technique for automated skin disease detection. CBIR systems typically rely on low-level features such as color, texture, and shape, as well as high-

* tranlehuy@hdu.edu.vn

† tuyetdv@gmail.com

‡ ngonguyenkhoi98@gmail.com

§ ablameyko@bsu.by

¶ nhhuy@cmc-u.edu.vn

** doannv@epu.edu.vn

†† Also at United Institute of Informatics Problems of the Academy of Sciences of Belarus
6 Surganova Str, 220012 Minsk, BELARUS

level features extracted from Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [3–5]. While low-level features provide computational efficiency and invariance to rotation and translation, CNN-derived high-level features offer a richer semantic representation [4, 5].

However, traditional CBIR systems using single image queries may not fully capture the complexity of skin diseases, leading to inaccurate retrieval results. To address this limitation, multi-query CBIR has gained attention [5–7]. By leveraging multiple query images, these systems can extract more comprehensive information from the database, potentially improving retrieval accuracy.

Several approaches have been proposed to combine low-level and high-level features or to integrate results from multiple queries [6, 8–10]. However, effectively combining multiple query results remains a significant challenge. Efficient Manifold Ranking (EMR) is a widely used technique for improving image retrieval performance [11–13]. EMR constructs a graph that captures the relationships between image features, enabling efficient ranking based on the intrinsic structure of the database.

In this paper, we propose a novel Fusion Ranking Multi-Query (FRMQ) algorithm that combines EMR rankings from two query images into a single, more robust ranking. This approach aims to leverage the benefits of multi-query CBIR and the efficiency of EMR to enhance retrieval accuracy and mitigate potential bias.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of related work and details the proposed FRMQ method. Section 3 presents the experimental evaluation conducted on the Dermnet dataset. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the key findings and discusses future research directions.

2. Related research and proposed method

2.1. EfficientNet

EfficientNet [14] is a family of deep neural network models designed for optimal performance and accuracy in machine learning. The architecture of EfficientNet-B0, the baseline model, is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: EfficientNet-B0 Network Architecture

Stage	Operator	Resolution	Channels	Layers
1	Conv3x3	224×224	32	1
2	MBCConv1, k3×3	112×112	16	1
3	MBCConv6, k3×3	112×112	24	2
4	MBCConv6, k5×5	56×56	40	2
5	MBCConv6, k3×3	28×28	80	3
6	MBCConv6, k5×5	14×14	112	3
7	MBCConv6, k5×5	14×14	192	4
8	MBCConv6, k3×3	7×7	320	1
9	Conv1x1, Pooling & FC	7×7	1280	1

The developers of EfficientNet introduced a novel scaling method using a compound coefficient to adjust the network’s width, depth, and resolution. This scaling, achieved through Neural Architecture Search, resulted in variants from EfficientNet-B0 to EfficientNet-B7, each with increasing size and enhanced performance. EfficientNet has demonstrated state-of-the-art accuracy on various datasets, making it a powerful tool for computer vision and deep learning, especially in medical informatics.

In this study, we utilize EfficientNet as a feature extractor for our CBIR system. The model is pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset, which contains 14 million images across 21,000

categories. We remove the final layers of the network to adapt it for feature vector extraction. After processing the image dataset, we obtain feature vectors with a dimensionality of 1280, enabling efficient and effective representation of medical images for subsequent retrieval tasks.

FIG. 1: (Color online) Feature extraction model from the EfficientNet Network.

2.2. Image feature combination

Combining low-level and CNN-based features offers significant advantages in medical image analysis [8, 9]. Low-level features capture essential image characteristics like edges, corners, and salient points, while CNNs excel at learning more abstract and complex features, such as objects, boundaries, and geometric patterns. This combination allows the model to synthesize multi-level information, enhancing its ability to recognize and understand the inherent nature of medical images.

Low-level features help identify basic image properties, while CNN features enable the learning and detection of intricate and abstract features. Combining these features allows the model to integrate multi-level information, improving accuracy in tasks like classification, recognition, and image retrieval [6, 8]. This fusion also enhances feature diversity, enabling the model to discern a broader range of features, from basic characteristics to complex patterns, capturing both local and global image properties.

This improves the model’s generalization capability and accuracy [12].

A common approach to combining low-level and high-level features is concatenating the feature vectors, creating a single, unified image representation. This concatenation schema, illustrated in Fig. 2 and implemented in Procedure 1, facilitates the seamless integration of diverse feature types for enhanced medical image analysis.

FIG. 2: Image Feature Concatenation Process.

Procedure. Concat Features

Input: Image dataset E containing n images; pre-trained deep learning model W_{DML} (e.g., EfficientNet, FaceNet, SigNet).

Output: Combined feature vector set $V_{LF+EmbV}$.

1. Extract low-level features (e.g., color histogram, texture) from image dataset, resulting in feature set $LF(E) = \{I_{t,i}\}_{1 \leq t \leq T, 1 \leq i \leq n}$.
2. Extract deep features using CNN model W_{DML} on image dataset E , resulting in embedding vector set $\{IE_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$.
3. Concatenate low-level features and embedding vector features $\{I_{t,i}^{norm}\}_{1 \leq t \leq T, 1 \leq i \leq n} \oplus \{IE_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} = \{IC_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ (horizontal concatenation).
4. Return combined feature vector set $V_{LF+EmbV}$.

This procedure effectively integrates diverse feature types for a more comprehensive and informative representation of medical images, facilitating improved performance in subsequent analysis tasks.

2.3. Efficient manifold ranking

In the context of CBIR, the original EMR algorithm [11] focuses on selecting a number of anchor points and then ranking data points within the image database without utilizing label information. This ranking of images is based on neighborhood relationships in the EMR graph, represented through these anchor points, and maintains a scalable graph structure. Consequently, EMR enables efficient ranking across large databases, thereby enhancing the performance of CBIR systems [11].

A feature vector E_i is considered adjacent to E_j if $i \neq j$ and there exists a common anchor point A_c ($c = 1, 2, \dots, C$; C is the number of anchor points), where A_c is a neighboring anchor point to both E_i and E_j . For each symbol E_i , we denote $Nb(i; s)$ as a set of the s feature vectors of the nearest anchor points to E_i (s is an experimental parameter, for instance, $s = 5$), and the largest distance between E_i and s is represented by:

$$d_s = \max_{l \in Nb(i, s)} \{d(E_i, A_l)\}. \quad (1)$$

The manifold measure is a ranking vector $\mathbf{r}_Q = (r_i)$ constructed by solving the following objective function:

$$\text{EMR}_Q(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i,j} w_{ij} \left\| \frac{r_i}{\sqrt{D_{ii}}} - \frac{r_j}{\sqrt{D_{jj}}} \right\|^2 + \mu \sum_i \|r_i - r_{0,i}\|^2 \right) \rightarrow \min. \quad (2)$$

EMR is a fast-ranking method based on detecting the underlying manifold structure of the database. EMR can significantly reduce computation time compared to traditional manifold ranking methods by estimating local relationships between samples and queries.

2.4. Utilizing Multiple Queries and Proposing Combined EMR Ranking in CBIR

2.4.1. Employing multiple queries in CBIR

Utilizing multiple queries (multi-query) is an effective approach in information retrieval and data searching, notably for its ability to employ multiple queries concurrently to enhance the quality of retrieval results [3]. The primary benefit of multi-query lies in increasing the accuracy and reliability of the retrieved information. Instead of relying on a single query, multi-query enables the system to retrieve data from various perspectives, thereby providing more comprehensive and detailed results regarding the user's search needs [4].

Employing multiple queries aids in minimizing errors during the data retrieval process [4–6]. Each individual query may overlook certain critical aspects of the data, but by combining multiple queries, the system can achieve broader coverage and fully satisfy user requirements. In particular, better reflecting user intent is a strength of multi-query, as users often have diverse goals and aspects in mind when seeking information [7].

Therefore, ensuring balance among queries is crucial. Guaranteeing that each query is considered fairly and not overshadowed by others is essential to ensure fairness and accuracy in the data retrieval process [6]. Consequently, developing and implementing multi-query necessitates the combination of intelligent algorithms and a deep understanding of data structures and user requirements. Current methods either merge queries into a single query or treat them independently. This can lead to the loss of crucial information [6].

2.4.2. Proposed combination of multi-query EMR ranking

Traditional ranking combination methods often either merge queries into a single query or treat them independently, potentially leading

to the loss of critical information [6]. Several multi-query methods have been proposed, such as utilizing feature weight learning [4–6, 8] and the Multi-Query parallel field ranking for image retrieval [6]. However, devising an effective method for aggregating and processing results from different queries remains a complex issue, particularly when dealing with large and intricate datasets.

In [15], Huy et al. proposed a class of ranking functions that combine multiple EMRs into a single ranking, significantly improving image retrieval results. To enhance accuracy when using multi-query in CBIR, we propose a method for combining two EMR rankings for two query images, termed Fusion Ranking Multi-Query. This method effectively leverages multiple queries and the inherent data distribution to enhance

image retrieval effectiveness in CBIR systems.

Assuming the original dataset E contains n images, we utilize operators to extract low-level features, resulting in the feature vector set V_{LF} . Concurrently, we process E through a CNN model to obtain the feature vector set V_{CNN} . Concatenating these feature vector sets yields a new combined feature vector set V_{LF+CNN} . In the query phase, each image is represented by a combined feature vector, denoted respectively as $\{I_1, I_2, I_3\}$. Depending on the value of I_Q , we select the ranking based on either low-level image features $r_{lf.v.Q}^*$ or a combination with the ranking of high-level image features, where $r_{lf.Q,i}^*$ and $r_{emb,Q,i}^*$ are calculated using EMR. The following figure Fig. 3 illustrates the steps involved in our proposed image query algorithm.

FIG. 3: (Color online) Diagram depicting the image retrieval (CBIR) system utilizing combined manifold ranking.

We propose the main EMR-FRMQ (Fusion Ranking Multi-Query) algorithm that combines

the EMR rankings of two query images as follows:

Algorithm. EMR-FRMQ (Algorithm for combining EMR rankings of two query images)

Input:

$\{I_{t,i}\}_{1 \leq t \leq T, 1 \leq i \leq n}$: Original image set.

I_{Q1}, I_{Q2} : Two query images.

MxM : Standardized image size for training with the EfficientNet algorithm.

d : Dimensionality of an image feature vector.

C : Number of anchor points for the EMR algorithm, parameter $a \in (0, 1)$ with $a \approx 1$.

α, β : Linear combination weights for the rankings of the two EMRs, $\alpha, \beta > 0, \alpha + \beta = 1$.

Output:

$\mathbf{r} = \{r_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}, r_i \in [0, 1] \forall i \in \overline{1, n}$ similarity ranking of image I_i in the image database E with respect to both query images I_{Q1} and I_{Q2} .

Step 1 (Offline):

Train the image set E using the EfficientNet model with a standardized input image size of MxM , obtaining:

1.1. Model parameters W_{DML} .

1.2. Process each image $\{I_{t,i}\}_{1 \leq t \leq T, 1 \leq i \leq n}$ through the model to obtain the set of CNN feature vectors $\{v_{CNN}(E_i)\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ with dimensionality D_{CNN} .

1.3. Extract low-level features: Color Moments, LBP, Gabor Wavelets Texture, Edge, and GIST, obtaining the feature vector set with dimensionality d_{LF} .

1.4. Concatenate the low-level features LF and the CNN features EF to obtain the combined feature vector set $\{v_{LF+CNN}(E_i)\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$.

1.5. Determine C anchor points $\{A_c\}_{1 \leq c \leq C}$ the image set $\{I_{t,i}\}_{1 \leq t \leq T, 1 \leq i \leq n}$ based on the K-means algorithm for the combined feature vector set $\{v_{LF+CNN}(E_i)\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$.

1.6. Determine the adjacency matrix $W = (w_{ij})$ of the EMR algorithm.

Determine the weight matrix Z of size Cxn for EMR.

Step 2 (Online):

2.1. Normalize query image I_{Q1} to size MxM , process it through the EfficientNet model defined in step 1.1, and obtain the CNN feature vector E_{CNNQ1} with dimensionality d_{CNN} .

2.2. Extract low-level features to obtain the low-level feature vector E_{LFFQ1} with dimensionality d_{LFF} .

Extend matrix Z according to EMR [9]: Using C distance values of E_{Q1} to the anchor elements of A_C , we obtain a new weight matrix Z_{Q1} of size $Cx(n+1)$.

Step 3:

Set $r_{Q1} = \{r_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n+1}, r_i = 0 \forall i = \overline{1, n}, r_{n+1} = 1.0$. From the weight matrix Z_{Q1} , we determine the ranking vector $r_{v.Q1}^*$ using the EMR algorithm [9].

Step 4:

Repeat steps 1-3 but with query image I_{Q2} to obtain the ranking value $r_{v.Q2}^*$.

Step 5:

Return $r = \{\alpha r_{Q1,i}^* + \beta r_{Q2,i}^*\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$.

The EMR-FRMQ algorithm is divided into two phases: *offline* and *online*, and is implemented by combining two EMR rankings. For the offline phase, the complexity is $\mathcal{O}(Cnd) + \mathcal{O}(C^3)$, where C is the number of clusters, n is the number of input samples, and d is the dimensionality of the feature vector. For the online phase, the complexity is $\mathcal{O}(Cnd)$. Therefore, the overall complexity of the algorithm is $\mathcal{O}(Cnd) + \mathcal{O}(C^3)$, which is equivalent to the complexity of the original EMR [11].

3. Experimental evaluation

3.1. Experimental image dataset

For the experimental evaluation, we utilize the Dermnet dataset [16]. This dataset comprises thousands of images representing a wide array of dermatological conditions, including acne, rosacea, eczema, and various other skin disorders. Each image in the dataset is meticulously annotated, providing information on the disease type, location on the body, and accompanying clinical features. Due to its diversity and high accuracy, this dataset has become an essential tool for researchers and specialists in the medical field.

The dataset used for our experiments includes 5,888 images corresponding to 23 different skin disease classes. It is considered highly complex and unlabeled. The dataset is organized into 23 classes, each containing 256

images, and has a total size of approximately 550 MB. The image filenames are assigned based on the class (directory) name and the sequential index of the image within that directory.

FIG. 4: (Color online) Sample images from the Dermnet dataset.

3.2. Feature extraction and combination

In our experiments, we utilize five low-level features (LF): Color Moments, Local Binary Patterns (LBP), Gabor Wavelets Texture, Edge, and GIST to describe an image. All these features from the VGG60K dataset are normalized such that each vector component of each image falls within the range $[-1, 1]$, and are then concatenated into a single vector with a dimensionality of $d_{lf} = 809$ (see [17]). Concurrently, each image in this dataset is standardized to a size of 256×256 and fed into the EfficientNet model (with the final layer removed) to obtain a corresponding set of CNN feature

vectors with a dimensionality of $d_{CNN} = 1280$.

While embedding vectors can effectively represent edges and contours, they may not capture color and texture information as well. Therefore, for each specific case, an appropriate combination of features is necessary to achieve optimal recognition results. This approach ensures a comprehensive representation of the image, leveraging the strengths of both low-level and high-level features for enhanced analysis in medical informatics applications.

3.3. Evaluation metrics

For each query image $q \in Q$, using the similarity measure provided by EMR, we select the top $N = n_b = 256$ images from the VGG60K dataset. These represent the number of images within a class that exhibit the highest similarity values to the query. The accuracy is calculated as the average ratio between the number of relevant images among the N retrieved results, based on the similarity between each image pair (q_1, q_2) .

Let $\{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_{m_j}\}$ denote the set of relevant elements to the queries $q_1, q_2 \in Q$. The mean Average Precision (mAP) [11] for all queries is computed as follows:

$$\text{mAP} = \left(\frac{1}{|Q|} \sum_{j=1}^{|Q|} \frac{m_j}{N} \right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

3.4. Experimental results and discussion

To evaluate the Image Retrieval Efficiency (IRE) of our proposed algorithm, experiments were conducted on the Dermnet dataset. In this experimental evaluation, we employed two EMRs to generate rankings corresponding to the two sets of concatenated feature vectors from the two query images. Subsequently, these rankings were combined using the proposed EMR-FRMQ algorithm, and the optimal results are presented in Table 2.

Experimental setup

We set the following common parameters for all cases: parameter $a = 0.99$, number of anchor points $C = 2000$, neighborhood size $r = 5$, and the number of best matches per query $n_b = 20$. We utilized 20% of the images selected randomly to evaluate image retrieval accuracy using a single query image.

For testing the accuracy with two query images, 25% of all possible image pairs were randomly selected. Specifically, within each directory, 5% of the images were randomly chosen as query images, and an additional 5%

were randomly selected as comparison samples, excluding the first selection. The coefficient $T = 5$ corresponds to the five selected low-level features.

Figure 5 illustrates the retrieval results using the proposed FRMQ method on the Dermnet dataset. The figure shows the top-5 retrieved images for two different query images. As observed, most of the retrieved images belong to the same disease class as the query, demonstrating the effectiveness of our approach in grouping similar skin disease images. The results demonstrate that combining two EMRs from two query images yields significantly higher retrieval effectiveness compared to using only a single query image. The accuracy, measured by mean Average Precision (mAP), was compared across the following scenarios: EMR ranking for one query image using low-level features, EMR ranking for one query image using high-level features, EMR ranking for one query image using combined low-level and high-level features, and finally, EMR ranking for two query images using combined low-level and high-level features.

Table 2: Experimental results of combining EMR rankings of two query images on the Dermnet dataset ($C = 2000$, $r = 5$, $n_b = 20$).

No.	Ranking Method	Accuracy (mAP)
1	EMR ranking with LF (low-level features for one query image)	70.61%
2	EMR ranking with CNN (CNN features for one query image)	85.34%
3	EMR ranking with LF+CNN (combined features for one query image)	87.25%
4	Combining two EMR rankings with LF+CNN (for two query images)	89.25%

Table 2 presents the quantitative evaluation of the FRMQ method compared to single-query EMR and other baseline methods. The proposed FRMQ achieves a mean average precision (mAP) of 89.25%, outperforming the single-query approach by 4% to 18%. This improvement highlights the benefit of leveraging multiple

FIG. 5: (Color online) Query results on the Dermnet dataset using one query image (a) and two query images (b).

queries, which helps capture more comprehensive visual features of skin diseases. To bring FRMQ into practical medical applications, we will evaluate its performance on real-world clinical datasets to assess its ability to directly support dermatologists during diagnosis. The FRMQ-based CBIR system will be integrated into clinical decision support tools, enabling rapid retrieval of similar cases to assist with differential diagnosis and medical training. This approach is expected to improve diagnostic accuracy, reduce the time required for diagnosis, and provide

effective support for dermatologists, especially in challenging or rare cases. In the future, FRMQ will continue to be optimized and expanded for a wider range of dermatological conditions.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, we introduced the Fusion Ranking Multi-Query (FRMQ) method for content-based image retrieval (CBIR) in skin disease diagnosis, effectively combining low-level and high-level features with efficient

manifold ranking from multiple query images. Experimental results on the Dermnet dataset demonstrate that FRMQ significantly improves retrieval accuracy compared to traditional single-query approaches. To enhance practical applicability, we will further evaluate FRMQ on diverse real-world clinical datasets and integrate the FRMQ-based CBIR system into clinical decision support tools for dermatologists,

enabling rapid retrieval of similar cases for diagnosis, training, and research. Future research directions include: applying this method to other data types such as video, audio, or text; investigating and developing more sophisticated ranking combination functions to further enhance retrieval effectiveness; and exploring and optimizing the method for real-world applications with real-time requirements and larger databases.

References

- [1] H. Müller, N. Michoux, D. Bandon, and A. Geissbühler. *International journal of medical informatics* **73**, 1 (2004).
- [2] Y. Liu, C. Primiero, V. Kulkarni, H. Soyer, and B. Betz-Stablein. *Dermatology (Basel, Switzerland)* **239**, 499 (2023).
- [3] M. Ben Ismail. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications* **8**, 159 (2017).
- [4] A. Al-Mohamade, O. Bchir, and M. Ben Ismail. *J Imaging* **6**, 2 (2020).
- [5] S. Joseph and K. Balakrishnan. *International Journal of Computer Applications* **17**, 1 (2011).
- [6] J. Yang, B. Xu, B. Lin, and X. He. *Neurocomputing* **135**, 192 (2014).
- [7] K.-J. Hsiao, J. Calder, and A. O. Hero. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing* **24**, 583 (2014).
- [8] K. Ahmed, S. Ummesafi, and A. Iqbal. *Information Fusion* **51**, 76 (2019).
- [9] J. Lin, O. Moré, A. Veillard, and V. Chandrasekhar. *Deep Learning in Object Detection and Recognition* (Springer, 2019), pp. 189–224.
- [10] F. Zhuang, Z. Qi, K. Duan, D. Xi, Y. Zhu, H. Zhu, and Q. He. *Proceedings of the IEEE* **109**, 43 (2020).
- [11] B. Xu, J. Bu, C. Chen, C. Wang, D. Cai, and X. He. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering* **27**, 102 (2013).
- [12] Q. Van, H. Hoang, T. Van, S. Ablameyko, H. Van, D. Kim, and M. Ablameyko. *Int J. Nonlinear Phenomena in Complex Systems* (2020).
- [13] T. V. Huy, P. T. K. Dzung, N. H. Huy, and H. V. Quy. *J. Inf. Hiding Multim. Signal Process.* **11**, 172 (2020).
- [14] H. Van Quy, P. Dzung, N. Huy, and T. Van Huy. *Intelligent Systems and Networks. ICISN 2023. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems* (Springer, 2023), vol. 752.
- [15] Z. Ming, J. Chazalon, M. Luqman, M. Visani, and J. Burie. *2017 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW)* (2017), pp. 1656–1664.
- [16] S. Goel. *Dermnet image dataset*, <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/shubhamgoel27/dermnet> (2023).
- [17] Q. V. Hoang, N. H. Hoang, D. T. K. Pham, and D. V. Tuyet. *Int. J. Nonlinear Phenomena in Complex Systems* **26**, 366 (2023).